

OpenMC validation for neutron transport using quality assessed SINBAD benchmarks with equivalent MCNP and MCBEND models

by

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Abstract:

This project aimed to validate the Monte Carlo code OpenMC for neutron flux modelling, this was done by simulating models using the code and analysing the results in reference to experimental data. Two benchmark experiments from the SINBAD database were selected to be modelled in OpenMC based on their material involvement and quality assessment; and both concerned measurements of neutron flux as well as activation. MCNP models of these benchmarks were already provided as well as results from a MCBEND model for one of the benchmarks. The involvement of these alternative codes helped broaden understanding of the level of accuracy in OpenMC's results. Generally, OpenMC proved accurate in its neutron flux tallying although a tendency for overestimation was consistently seen for both benchmarks. For the first benchmark OpenMC derived a total flux C/M ratio of (1.06 ± 0.01) , and for the second benchmark ratios of (0.95 ± 0.01) , (1.10 ± 0.01) and (1.40 ± 0.01) . Results from the MCNP and MCBEND codes proved more accurate for the first benchmark, although for the second benchmark OpenMC was marginally more accurate than MCNP. The subsequent activation measurements from OpenMC mostly followed the trend of minor overestimation, except for one detector in the second benchmark model where the reaction rates were significantly overestimated. This project concluded OpenMC's neutron transport capability appeared viable but recommended further investigation due to some of the overestimation's observed.

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1 Introduction

This project predominantly reviews the neutron transport modelling efficacy of the Monte Carlo code OpenMC. By performing simulations with this code a comparison of results can be made against real life experimental measurements, as well as from equivalent simulations produced by the alternative Monte Carlo codes MCNP and MCBEND.

During power operations fission events occur throughout a reactor core due to the presence of fuel and a moderator. Neutrons are released during such fission events and travel throughout the reactor, not only inducing further fission reactions, but also interacting with the surrounding material and structure. Understanding the transport of the neutrons is therefore vital for safe and economical running, where interactions such as neutron irradiation and activation have consequences for the engineering requirements of the reactor. More practical effects such as personnel dose and reactor pressure vessel lifetime depletion are also important considerations for the real-life management of a nuclear reactor facility.

Therefore, neutron transport modelling is done not only to support the safe operation of the reactor but also to aid understanding of the neutron transport behaviour in a computer model vs reality context. Confidence in such models and their outputs can be broadly maintained through the understanding of the implicit code as well as nuclear particle behaviour. The long established MCNP code has an extensive history of use for modelling several reactor and shielding structures, but as a general-purpose code MCNP has seen many applications outside of the nuclear industry as well. The code MCBEND is also considered general purpose and has been extensively used in areas such as shielding and dosimetry, yet it does not possess the same level of scope or operational experience as MCNP; mainly since MCBEND is considerably younger than MCNP. However, restrictions on these Monte Carlo codes regarding security control and shareability have caused attention to turn to the open-source code OpenMC. This much more modern code has a considerable practical advantage against the aforementioned regarding ease of access, as it can be used on a cloud via virtual machines unlike many Monte Carlo codes that are used under proprietary licensing.

And so, this project was setup to validate OpenMC in terms of its neutron flux modelling and hopefully improve confidence that use of OpenMC can be effective. The SINBAD benchmarks are a reliable choice to evaluate OpenMC's treatment of neutron transport against real life experimental data. MCNP models of these benchmarks will also be used for deeper analysis of OpenMC's results in terms of code and data library comparison. Information on a MCBEND model and its results are also supplied for one of the benchmarks. Understanding of relative advantages and disadvantages between the codes, in extent of the predominant shareability difference, would also prove insightful for deciding how to pursue the use of OpenMC.

Ultimately, this project reviews OpenMC throughout the simulation of two benchmark experiments, and hopes to prove OpenMC can be validated for its neutron transport capabilities. Also, this project brings more in-depth insight into the functioning, and troubleshooting, involved in Monte Carlo simulations and the results analysis process by comparing the simulation results to genuine experimental data.

2 Theory

2.1 The Monte Carlo Method

The term Monte Carlo method refers to any form of computational algorithm in which repeated random sampling is used to obtain a numerical value instead of deterministic methods. This methodology was first invented by Stanislaw Ulam whilst working on nuclear weapons projects at Los Alamos National Laboratory in the late 1940's [1]. As a sampling technique inherent randomness is a key aspect of this methodology [2], and this is done by sampling from probability distributions [3]. Either way, Monte Carlo based experiments repeat this sampling several times to converge upon numerical results; hence, they can approximate solutions to problems that are too complex to analyse mathematically. Such experiments fall into three distinct problem classes of sampling, estimation and optimization. This project concerns the first two types where a simulation model mimics the real-life behaviour of particles through repeated realizations (sampling) and numerical quantities are estimated from the model (estimation) [4].

Monte Carlo methods are often implemented using computer simulations and so are commonly utilised in the nuclear industry to model radiation transport through a specified geometry. Given their complexity but also adaptability these methods are heavily used in this industry for simulations in many areas of interest, such as shielding and radio-biology, and can provide extremely insightful information on nuclear systems. These methods have also found use outside of the nuclear industry in mathematics, statistics, finance, and even social sciences with the potential to model any real-life random system that is not particle transport based. For example, Monte Carlo simulations could reflect inventory processes, vehicle routing, stock portfolios and so forth [4].

In this project Monte Carlo methodology is used to simulate the transport of neutrons in shielding models. Neutron transport theory would instead use the fundamental Boltzmann equation as a description of the neutrons behaviour, this is defined as a continuity statement so in equation 1 the neutron population is in a steady state. This is mathematically represented by the imbalance term of $1/v \delta\varphi/\delta t$, the remaining left-hand side therefore describes neutron loss through collisions as the flux φ to the total neutron cross section Σ_t , and also abandonment of the phase space without interaction by the streaming term $\Omega \cdot \nabla\varphi$. Hence, the right hand side of equation 1 describes the supply of neutrons through extraneous (non-fission) sources in $S(r, E, \Omega, t)$, and from scattering into the phase space of interest as $(E' \rightarrow E, \Omega' \rightarrow \Omega)$ [5].

$$1/v \frac{\delta\varphi}{\delta t} + \Omega \cdot \nabla\varphi + \Sigma_t(r, E)\varphi(r, E, \Omega, t) = \int d\Omega' \int dE' \Sigma_s(E' \rightarrow E, \Omega' \rightarrow \Omega)\varphi(r, E', \Omega', t) + S(r, E, \Omega, t) \quad (1)$$

Deterministic methods for particle transport solve equation 1 in a numerically approximated manner everywhere throughout a system. Often assumptions involving the geometry and particle nature (such as the one-speed approximation or diffusion model[5]) are required to make equation 1 actually solvable for a particular system. Therefore, Monte Carlo simulations provide an alternative stochastic method for particle transport that does not require such assumptions or simplifications, rather the system can be modelled almost exactly [6].

Within a model defined by Monte Carlo methods, a simulation would be run that involves producing histories of particles by the generation of random numbers and sampling from nuclear data probability distributions, most notably cross-sectional data but energetic, directional, and spatial distributions of radiation are also used. The individual probabilistic events are simulated sequentially to describe particle behaviour in an 'event log' manner. Such 'steps' are associated to random sampling from such probability distributions to determine the outcome at each step. Figure 1 shows a physical diagram of this alongside an event log of a particles journey in terms of interactions and movement. When a particle leaves the system or is destroyed in a reaction (as in step 2's fission reaction) then its history is complete.

Figure 1: Depiction of a particle's journey as logged as a 'history' in Monte Carlo simulations [7].

The particles history is monitored using a combination of appropriate physics and randomness in order to mimic reality. With a collection of such particles this process can

be described mathematically as a summation of particles that have their own physical weighting X_i , and with a high enough number of particles N a resulting integration is produced from an initially discrete sampling as shown in equation 2.

$$\sum_{i=1}^N X_i/N \rightarrow \int^N X_i/N = X \quad (2)$$

$$P(X_i) = 1/\sqrt{2\pi X} \exp(-(X_i - X)^2/2X) \quad (3)$$

Due to the large number of histories modelled, equation 2 also demonstrates how the sampling distribution of the particles has converged under the central limit theorem [8]. The output X is the mathematical mean from a normal distribution (defined by equation 3 [9]) of the mean values taken repeatedly from each history. X will have an error of standard deviation $\sigma(X)$, which in a normal distribution will be proportional to the number of histories N as $1/\sqrt{N}$. The error can be used to evaluate the precision of the simulation as an inherently standard normal distribution (rather than accuracy which would depend on the physical value with regards to what is being modelled). Guidance on the permitted level of error is shown in table 1 that depicts the error range and associated tally quality, with the main takeaway being that error above 10% deems the tally result unreliable.

Range of Error (fractional)	Quality of Tally
0.50 to 1.00	Not meaningful
0.20 to 0.50	Factor of a few out
0.10 to 0.20	Questionable
< 0.10	Generally Reliable
< 0.05	Generally Reliable for point detectors

Table 1: Table detailing the tally error ranges in terms of quality and validity of the result [7].

The error returned can most simply be reduced by an increase in N and therefore computational runtime, yet in practice this is often limited by computer budgets. Despite being recognised to be of immense technological use, Monte Carlo methods require a major trade-off between accuracy and computational expense where long simulation runtimes can prove impractical and costly. The reliability of random number generators and validation of results are also recognised limitations. Therefore, methods of variance reduction are often employed to reduce the computational demand and improve the efficiency of the simulation by reducing the associated errors on the tallies.

The concept of truncation, that is limiting parts of phase space that do not contribute significantly to the solution, is a key method of variance reduction. This can be done in terms of geometry by excluding unimportant elements of the model, but energy and time as direct cutoffs can also be used [7]. Truncating the model in this way increases N by localising the particles to a desirable phase space, such as a detector region that only records particles of a certain energy range within a certain time frame. Other techniques respond to the particles properties of weight and importance in the model; these are determined by the particles locality within the phase space in reference to the tallying procedure. Importance is more descriptive of the actual probability that a particle will cause a tally, so as a particle gets nearer the detector it becomes more 'important'. Whereas the weight of a particle concerns how well the particle models the physical system of the simulation. Hence, a particle splitting because it has become so important will then constitute two particles of weights 0.5 each.

Modified sampling methods directly improve the efficiency of the tallying process by increasing the statistical sampling of the simulation. For example, the directional sampling is instead done from a distribution to send particles more mono-directionally towards the detector rather than isotropically. This modification to the physical probabilities requires appropriate adjustment to the weighting of the particles to keep the simulation and its results unbiased.

Population control methods apply this methodology directly to the particles by choosing to 'kill' them off or multiplying them in the simulation, this is achieved by techniques of rouletting and splitting respectively [7]. This method is often associated with the individual weightings the particles possess in the phase space, so population control methods can be used to influence the number of samples taken in specific regions e.g more particles in the region of the detector. Again, weight adjustment is required to ensure that any estimations made from the simulation are unbiased when using population control variance reduction.

One common population control method is that of weight windows, where user defined 'windows' are added in the geometry and set to respond accordingly to the weight of any particles entering. The weight windows technique was developed with the intention to reduce error on tallies far from the tally region by allowing the user to define weight allowances within a mesh structure over the model [10]. OpenMC has the capability for such mesh geometry to be a rectilinear, cylindrical or spherical structure, and each 'window' of the mesh is assigned upper and lower weight boundaries[11]. When entering a 'window' the particle's weight will react against the bounds set; in the case of the weight exceeding the upper bound, the particle is split into N particles as determined by equation 4.

$$N = \min(N_{max}, [w/w_u]) \quad (4)$$

If, however, the weight is below the bounds, the particle is instead rouletted with a minimum weight cutoff also being applied, below which the particle would be instantly killed. Ultimately this can be manipulated by the user to encourage tallying at the detector and improve the efficiency of the simulation. As shown in figure 2, between the bounds there is an ‘acceptable’ weight window in which no action is taken. When out of windows bounds, the actions previously described adjust the weighting so that the remaining particles can exist within the window’s limits.

Figure 2: Diagram of the weight windows function where the particle has either met the windows bounds, or exceeded, or fallen short of and the actions taken [10].

When a particle does enter a tally or scoring region (usually the region modelling a detector) it is recorded and combined with a score coefficient to return the desired output. So not just the presence of the particle is recorded but a more useful quantity such as the neutron flux or rate of a particular reaction. Within the detector the weighted average is calculated to give the best estimate of this result, alongside the statistical error of $\sigma(X)$. Unlike deterministic techniques, the numerical result is provided by the average behaviour of many simulated particles, rather than from the average behaviour of a single particle as equation 1 describes [7].

$$Z = \int dr \int d\Omega \int dE f(r, \Omega, E) \Psi(r, \Omega, E) \quad (5)$$

Equation 5 describes the tallying process in terms of filters and scores as f and Ψ respectively, that produce the tally result Z (calculated across the phase space defined in particle direction Ω , energy E and position r) [11]. The filter f is the limits of what events can score based on attributes of the particle (e.g a specified cell or particle energy range in the phase space); and the score Ψ identifies a genuine physical quantity to be recorded from an event which matches to the specified filters (e.g particle flux, fission rate, secondary neutron production).

2.2 The OpenMC Code

Before reviewing any experimental bases or Monte Carlo simulations this project requires some context on OpenMC and the other codes being considered. Whilst much of the behaviour and treatment of neutrons will be undeniably similar if not identical in all three codes, some background knowledge on each of the codes history and any points of interest in their development and functioning will be advantageous, not necessarily for analysing their results, but for providing a wider understanding of each codes practical nature.

First developed at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology in 2011, OpenMC is a relative newcomer to the Monte Carlo coding community. While it by no means possesses the operational experience of long-standing codes such as MCNP, OpenMC does possess many features that may prove attractive for users and developers alike. OpenMC operates using portable file formats with XML files for the input, and the HDF5 format for the output [11]. OpenMC is unique in its use of a python API as the initial user input, where a python script is used for the user written text files that are then compiled to the input XML files. The python API allows for parameterisation which is advantageous for bringing simplification and adaptability to values used in the input text, as well as useful python based tools such as loop functions.

As with many older codes, in MCNP the user writes the code input directly as coded language, in a similar vein to Fortran punch card codes, to provide all the required specifications. Contrary to OpenMC's python API in MCNP a defined variable is hard-wired and would require manual alteration to change throughout the entire input. The separation OpenMC imposes between the written input and the XML files does allow users a more free-form approach to the text file structure, as well as the syntax being more readable to an untrained eye. This certainly makes OpenMC more user-friendly and applicable to a wider audience in comparison to older codes like MCNP. However, the disconnection in OpenMC's inputs files has met challenges in quality assurance procedures as the files could be made inconsistent (e.g the XML file could be altered manually without rerunning the python script).

Another significant difference between the codes is the level of purpose their particle transport capabilities allow them. MCNP is a general-purpose code that allows up to 37 particle types to be tracked over a broad range of energies, hence it's wide use within and outside of the nuclear industry [12]. MCBEND is also considered general purpose with neutron, gamma ray and electron transport capability [13]. But OpenMC's capability is limited to simulating only neutral particles (neutrons and photons) and therefore has more limited applications.

As mentioned in section 2.1, variance reduction techniques are useful methods for improving the efficiency of a simulation and so most Monte Carlo codes will have a variety of techniques available, as well as different user defined ways of implementing them.

For many years after its release OpenMC's variance reduction options consisted solely of survival biasing, which is rather limited as a population control method as it cannot guide particles to a certain region, this technique may also introduce undesirable particle weight fluctuation. Hence, the common weight windows function was developed for OpenMC to accelerate calculations and their efficiencies, particularly in deep penetration shielding models [10]. The code MCBEND also uses techniques of particle splitting and rouletting within its multi-map functionality, where energy and space dependent importance's overlay the geometry in a splitting mesh that acts upon the particles [14]. Yet the code MCNP contains much broader tools of variance reduction with methods of truncation, population control, modified sampling, and even partially deterministic types available. Hence, one could certainly claim there is much more user choice when perfecting simulation efficiency in MCNP (variance reduction techniques specific to this project will be addressed in section 3).

Unlike MCNP and many other high standard Monte Carlo codes, OpenMC is freely available as an open-source code that encourages scientific collaboration and adaptation. This is advantageous in the sense that OpenMC benefits from quick intellectual development as well as ease of availability and no licensing requirements. However, this free-for-all nature does raise questions regarding the due management and quality assurance of this code. As with any open source software, the development of the OpenMC code largely falls onto a community of developers rather than any single authority. Whereas codes owned under proprietary, such as the Los Alamos National Laboratory owned MCNP, have much more controlled development and maintenance where issues such as bugs found in the code have a formal process of reporting and resolution. Which methodology is more effective at improving the code is rather subjective, but the latter definitely lends itself to more effective quality assurance and accountability.

Overall, OpenMC's modern standing brings with it many advantages not least of which is a code that is far more collaborative and accessible than many of its predecessors, in terms of practical usability the learning curve for MCNP is clearly steeper. Evidently, the OpenMC code requires time and further development to achieve the capability of other Monte Carlo codes that produce quality results, for example the limited variance reduction techniques is a major drawback of OpenMC. However, this project hopes OpenMC can prove itself just as adept and reliable for neutron transport modelling.

2.3 The SINBAD Benchmarks

The Shielding Integral Benchmark Archive and Database (SINBAD [15]) was started in the 1990s by the OECD/NEA Data Bank and RSICC (Radiation Safety Information Computational Centre) with the intent to preserve results of several radiation shielding experiments in an easily accessible, standardised format [16]. The database details 102 shielding benchmarks associated to fission reactor shielding (48 benchmarks), fusion blanket neutronics (31 benchmarks), and accelerator shielding (23 benchmarks). This database has served a variety of uses outside of just academic and research-based interest, SINBAD has also seen very practical uses by nuclear data evaluators, computer code developers and experiment designers.

It was established early in SINBAD's development that the benchmark experiments were meant to be computationally reproducible and therefore provide comparable results between experiment and model. Ideally this will aid understanding of nuclear systems by analysis of the calculated to measured ratio (and their variances) for several parameters relevant to nuclear shielding such as dose, cross sections, reaction rate etc by validation against the SINBAD data. This validation against the benchmark experiments can be used to provide user confidence in the performance of their data and computer coded models [16].

A single benchmark in the database should contain a complete description of the source, geometry, measurements and examples of the transport and cross section sensitivity and uncertainty analysis. The number of Monte Carlo codes that have been used for SINBAD benchmarks is extensive and not limited to stochastic methods but also includes deterministic codes such as DOT, but the long-established MCNP code is a very prominent presence.

Since 2007, a quality review process has been undertaken on the database to review the quality of the existing data and experimental descriptions. This was motivated by the need to reconsider how useful the benchmarks truly are against today's high quality cross section evaluations (as some benchmark experiments were conducted as far back as the 1960s). Judgement of the benchmark quality required evaluation of the benchmark's standards based on the description of the experiment, details of original documentation, uncertainties of physical parameters and the procedure used to derive the data. Hence, any gaps in the experimental descriptions that may impact any modelling of the benchmarks were identified. The review also involved deriving new experimental information from the SINBAD literature, and refinement of the source models for modern codes such as MCNP5/X and PHITS in order to reproduce the experiment as exact as reasonably possible [16].

Due to much variance between the individual experiments, and not just the aforementioned age, the benchmarks were found to be of varying quality and were ranked by the following three classifications:

- 1) Benchmarks as valid for nuclear data and code bench marking.
- 2) Benchmarks of intermediate quality suitable for education and training.
- 3) Benchmarks of historical interest.

For a user of the SINBAD database the second classification calls for the application of common sense to complete the experimental information. More drastically for the third classification serious assumptions are required to complete the benchmark information [17]. Hence, only the first classification is regarded as appropriate for code validation whilst the other two standards classify benchmarks as more for educational purposes.

2.4 SINBAD Optioneering

In terms of this project, the benchmark models were to be used to assess the validity of the OpenMC codes simulation of neutron transport. For proper evaluation of OpenMC's neutron flux capability only benchmarks recognized to be of quality classification "one" (as described in section 2.3) were considered. The benchmarks used in this project were also selected on the criteria of material relevance to reactor design. Benchmarks that involved materials commonplace in reactor moderators, coolants and shields were sought as OpenMC's evaluation of neutron transport from these benchmarks would prove more useful in the hope that the validation could be advanced to reactor model study. On the other hand, these benchmarks may indicate such is unnecessary if OpenMC failed to adequately simulate neutron transport in those fundamental materials.

2.4.1 The Water Benchmark

The water benchmark experiment was conducted with the intention of measuring the fast neutron spectrum from neutrons moderated by light water, where several samples of Californium-252 provided the neutron source. The experimental setup consists of a large water-filled tank containing a central aluminium tube in which the measurements were made, and up to eight suspended source capsules surrounding the tube, figure 3 depicts a diagram of this arrangement.

The source capsules contain the source samples with stainless steel and void regions encapsulating them. An overhead support structure suspends the source capsules where the sources can be moved radially and axially with respect to the sample plane: that is the horizontal plane hosting the centre of the measurement sample. The nearest distance of a source to any boundary is approximately 38cm, more than four times the migration length of 5 MeV neutrons in light water and so the arrangement can be considered an infinite bath of water.

Figure 3: Diagram of the water tank used in the Winfrith water benchmark experiment with the measurement tube and sources shown within [18].

The experimental readings were made using an activation sulphur foil measuring the reaction rate of $S^{32}(n,p)P^{32}$ whilst an NE213 liquid scintillator measured the neutron spectrum above 1 MeV. The former is a threshold reaction so is recorded only above an energy of 0.639 MeV and the scintillator results were taken across 19 energy groups. The accompanying standard deviation errors are a quantification of the variability in the experimental results [18]. In terms of quality assessment, it was noted that the experiment description may allow for doubts regarding the bowing effects of the water tank, and no information is provided on the experimental hall nor on any possible background correction on the detector measurements [17].

As light water behaves as both moderator and coolant in an LWR, this benchmark's simplicity proved advantageous for reviewing code simulating neutron transport in light water. Some of the steel or aluminium components could be analysed with precise sample placement yet the experiment is very much focused on analysing neutron transport in water exclusively; where no results specific to the alternate materials are provided. Additionally, the results are specific to the fast neutron range exclusively above 1MeV and the experiment does not consider thermal scattering at all. Therefore, while this experiment will certainly bring insight into neutron transport with a water moderator/coolant, as well as OpenMC's handling of cross sections with the sulphur activation, the range of neutron energy that is comparable to experimental readings is somewhat limited.

2.4.2 The Janus Phase One Benchmark

The Janus program was conducted at the ASPIS facility in the late 1980s and intended to provide experimental data on the transport of neutrons through isotopes of steel and sodium, this was done to support the shielding aspect design of sodium-cooled fast reactors. In fast reactors neutron leakage is much more significant compared to thermal reactors due to the differences in the neutron energies and cross sections. The possible consequences of neutron irradiation and secondary activation of structures surrounding the reactor are undesirable and need to be mitigated with effective shielding [19]. More detail on the Janus phase one experiment's approach to this and comparison of fast and thermal neutron spectra is contained in appendix section 1.

The Neutron Source Thermal Reactor (NESTOR) was an experimental facility in Winfrith in which a water-cooled, water and graphite moderated reactor supported several experimental facilities. The reactor is surrounded by a graphite reflector block where behind each of the four faces lies an experiment cave. Figure 4 shows a diagram of cave C where the ASPIS facility is located, this is where shielding components are mounted vertically into a mobile tank structure to conduct neutron shielding experiments. It was here that many of the benchmark experiments concerned with nuclear fission shielding were performed; the water benchmark was also conducted at the Winfrith site but not in this experiment cave.

Figure 4: Diagram of the ASPIS facility with cave C extending from NESTOR reactor [20].

The ASPIS containment contains a highly enriched uranium-aluminium fission plate that behaves as a secondary fission source as a result of the neutrons leaking from the NESTOR core. The neutrons generated in the fission plate then propagate further into the shielding configuration. The shielding structure can be loaded with different material elements for experimental analysis into the neutron moderation and shielding properties of these materials.

Phase one of the program scrutinised mild and stainless steel with the use of an absolutely calibrated fission plate acting as the neutron source. The shielding array consisted of four distinct regions of source (the graphite moderator and fission plate), spectral filter (the preceding mild steel), the test region of stainless steel plates and finally the backing shield region of more mild steel; figure 5 shows this shielding arrangement diagrammatically with the accompanying texture key. The trolley structure contains this shielding configuration where the graphite portion is the barrier between the reactor and trolley, and this extends to the NESTOR reflector as indicated by the 'NESTOR' label in figure 5. The fission plate consists of a Uranium Aluminium alloy containing 93% enriched uranium within an aluminium frame, and the fuel loading is specifically arranged to mimic a disc fission source (detailed in section 3.2.2).

Figure 5: Diagram of the trolley structure within the ASPIS cave C facility, containing the shielding configuration of mild and stainless steel [20].

The detectors used included several activation foils located between the slab components of the shielding configuration. The Janus programme incorporated a varied selection of detectors measuring reaction rates of proton, secondary neutron and gamma production. For the phase one experiment measurements were made with $Mn55(n, \gamma)Mn56$ and $Au197(n, \gamma)Au198$ under cadmium, as well as the threshold detectors of $Rh103(n, n')Rh103$ and $S32(n, p)P32$. These were placed throughout the central axis of the disc fission source to provide penetration measurements and also at

vertical intervals of 25cm for lateral readings. As specified from the quality review process, the main drawback in the experimental description was established as the lack of detail regarding the detector configuration [15], indeed, reviews of the other Janus experiments occasionally found the detectors dimensions inconsistent [17]. Figure 6 shows the full complement of detector locations, which are all located in the air cavities between the shielding slabs.

Figure 6: Diagram of the trolley structure with the detector locations indicated by 'Bn' as well as any lateral offsets and their dimension [20].

Note that a fraction of the neutrons measured will be original leakage neutrons from the NESTOR reactor core instead of originating from the fission plate, and so this core component must be subtracted from the measurements. Background corrections were therefore applied to all the activation detectors. In addition to the neutron activation measurements taken from these foils, the neutron spectrum above 50KeV was measured by a group of spectrometers. This included hydrogen filled proportional counters each at different pressures to cover different neutron energy ranges, and a scintillator was used to measure above the 1 MeV range. These recorded the flux only at the B6, B10 and B14 locations with no lateral offset.

Note that the configuration may be modified slightly with regards to use of the detectors. For the insertion of the manganese detectors, the last slab of mild steel was removed so the concrete was preceded by air instead. Due to the spectrometers larger size than the foil and carrier structure, in order to insert the detectors at the penetration sites the preceding slab was removed and the next slab moved back the width of the air gap which separated it from the next plate. This will be revisited in section 3.1.1 where the shielding configuration needed to be modelled with these detector specific alterations.

Relative to the water benchmark this experiment involves the far less neutron moderating medium of steel (when compared to light water). This is advantageous for

evaluating OpenMC neutron transport capability in a material that interacts with neutrons quite differently to water, i.e the scattering process is depletes far less energy from the neutrons. Both materials are common in reactor structures and have influence on the neutron transport, steel will be more relevant for structural evaluations in a reactor whilst water more directly controls the fission process as the primary moderator in many reactor designs. Also, the shielding configuration means this model can be used to evaluate neutron moderation in the mild and stainless-steel material type, as different grades of steel are often incorporated in reactor structure. Whereas the water benchmark is specific to the light form of water when heavy water can also be used as an effective moderator/coolant.

3 Modelling

3.1 The Water Benchmark

3.1.1 The Experiment as a Model

Despite the experimental description in section 2.4.1, of the many source arrangements described in the experiment only one had a model provided with it: that is the specification of all eight sources at a distance of 25.4 cm to the detector with no vertical displacement. Hence, in the interest of having another code for comparison along with the experimental data only this arrangement was modelled with OpenMC. The sources were also set to be each of equal weighting by using relative weightings in the OpenMC source definition [11].

As a geometrical model the experiment can be modelled as a bath of water where the aluminium casing of the bath and the overhead steel support structure are irrelevant, as their emission does not introduce inaccuracy into the results due to the neutron migration length. The edges of the water tank are set as vacuum boundaries, meaning particles are ‘killed’ upon leaving the water tank and make no further contribution to the simulation. The rest of the surfaces are not set and so default to transmissive boundaries where particles pass through freely. Figure 7 show plots of the OpenMC water benchmark model in two different axes, where the Z plane is the vertical height in reference to the measurement tube.

Figure 7: Plots of the water benchmark model in the XY plane (left) and YZ plane (right), the colour coding assigns the water as blue, steel as grey, aluminium as brown with the sulphur/scintillator sample as pink and californium source as red. The right hand plot includes labels of the major components.

The model of figure 7 allows quite a straightforward variance reduction that can be applied to the water benchmark model with OpenMC's weight windows functionality. This was done as self-containing cylinders arranged as extending outwards from the central tube as far as the sources. OpenMC uses its weight windows function to encourage less rouletting and more splitting towards the detector and vice versa away from the central tube. The detector was modelled as a sample of sulphur or hydrocarbon composite for the scintillator contained within the central measurement tube. For the former the tallying recorded the $S32(n,p)P32$ reaction rate and the latter the neutron flux. OpenMC implicitly normalises to source particle but further normalisation needed to be done manually after the tallies had been collated from the simulation.

It is important to note that the OpenMC and MCNP simulations did not use equivalent cross sectional data libraries, but rather MCNP used the older ENDFB7.1 data library [21], whereas OpenMC used the more modern ENDF8.0 library [22]. Table 2 summarises all the data library's used in this project and their associated year of release [23]. While the choice of library should not make a significant difference in the tallying from any of the codes, it is worth considering if the newer libraries provide more accurate results. OpenMC's evaluation will not be limited to just the ENDF8.0 library in order to provide a more comprehensive understanding of this code and its results.

Library	Year of Release
ENDFB8.0	2018
ENDFB7.1	2011
JEFF2.2	1993
JEFF3.3	2017

Table 2: Table of data libraries used in this project alongside their respective years of release.

3.1.2 Source Definition

One of the most important aspects of the simulation's parameters was in defining the source spectrum to accurately describe the neutrons emission as per the experiment. The Watt spectrum is known as the distribution of energies of prompt neutrons from the fission of Uranium-235, (so is alternatively called the prompt neutron fission spectrum). This reaction releases 2.5 neutrons per fission and has a mean energy of approximately 2 MeV [24]. It is represented mathematically by equation 6 and is commonly used to described neutron emission from the fission process of several isotopes. Equation 7 describes an alternative model where the nuclear energy distribution is instead given by the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution [7] which the MCNP model used. This description characterizes the neutrons as a strongly diluted gas in thermal equilibrium with their surroundings, hence the parameter a is the temperature in MeV [5].

$$p(E) = C \exp(-E/a) \sinh(\sqrt{bE}) \quad (6)$$

$$p(E) = CE^{1/2} \exp(-E/a) \quad (7)$$

In both cases $p(E)$ is the direct probability of the emitted neutron from the fission event having energy E . Also, both have numerical coefficients C so that the output weights are normalised to 1, yet when provided with probability weightings OpenMC performs this normalisation anyway so this coefficient is not necessary to include in the data production. The equations are defined across the energy limits of the neutron emission spectrum, which are set as $E_{max} = 12.8$ MeV and $E_{min} = 0.0595$ MeV. Note that for the OpenMC simulation these boundaries were actually slightly altered when changing the probability distribution as explained for figure 9. Figure 8 shows several neutron emission spectra provided by the water benchmark's source definition.

Figure 8: Several emission spectra used to model the Californium-252 source in the water benchmark experiment: a purely numerical distribution (Experiment), Watt spectrum (Watt (Californium-252)) and a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution (Maxwell-Boltzmann (MCNP)) are shown.

The neutron emission as provided from the experimental description is directly taken from the spontaneous fission spectrum of Californium-252 [18]. A Watt spectrum imitating this with parameters of $a = 1.18$ and $b = 1.0342$ is also shown [7]. The MCNP simulations Maxwell-Boltzmann spectrum instead set a as 1.42. The similarities in shape are very apparent despite different respective weightings, where the experimental source calibration returned the most pronounced emission spectrum.

The experimental distribution is given by a histogram of energy bins to normalised emission strengths as the probability weightings, which each carry an error of 0.5% [18]. Originally the OpenMC model had this numerical distribution as the source spectrum, yet this was later converted from the original histogram form to a 'discrete ordinates' form. This converted was done by using the given weightings against the central energy of the associated bin. This was done after technical issues were found when incorporating a histogram distribution into the OpenMC code, see appendix section 3 for detail. Figure 9 shows the experimental distribution and OpenMC's new central bin defined discrete distribution for the source emission in the water benchmark.

Figure 9: The histogram experiment distribution (Experiment) is shown alongside the updated spectrum used in OpenMC (OpenMC (central bins)). As the latter uses the central energy of the former's' energy bins, a shift in energy between the distributions can be seen.

3.2 The Janus Phase One Benchmark

3.2.1 The Experiment as a Model

As a geometrical model Janus phase one appears as a series of boxes containing the materials of the shielding configuration as described in section 2.4.2. As well as the shielding slabs, the trolley face, fission plate and graphite region all need to be modelled as the source region of the model. Figure 10 shows the entire model as an OpenMC plot with the accompanying colour coding given in table 3.

Figure 10: Plot of the Janus phase one model from OpenMC in the XZ plane. The source region and shielding configuration extending to the concrete block are shown with labels indicating the fission plate, trolley face and fuel region. The fuel is contained within the fission plate and is indicated by table 3 as the dark green colour.

Material	Density (g/cm^3)	Colour
Mild Steel	7.835	Purple
Aluminium	2.700	Grey
Fuel	3.256	Dark Green
Graphite	1.650	Green
Aluminium	2.666	Brown
Mild Steel	7.850	Blue
Stainless Steel	7.917	Yellow
Stainless Steel	7.939	Pink
Stainless Steel	7.905	Red
Stainless Steel	7.921	Orange
Concrete	2.242	Silver

Table 3: Table defining the materials of the Janus phase one model in OpenMC.

Unlike the water benchmark model, there is no overall container as part of the Janus phase one model to act as a universe box with vacuum boundaries removing particles from the simulation. Therefore, one was added into the model manually as a box sitting just outside the trolley structure to encapsulate the entire shielding configuration. The rest of the surfaces are not set and so default to transmissive boundaries where particles pass through freely.

In between the shielding slabs the detectors are modelled as cylindrical structures that are attached to the appropriate shield block by aluminium carriers. Figure 11 shows this structure where the manganese or gold foils are contained within an outer cadmium casing. The rhodium detector sits the other side of this casing and attaches to the sulphur detector. The sulphur detector is by far the largest foil and the first component to be encountered by the source emission from the fission plate. As noted in section 2.4.2, due to vagueness regarding the detector configuration the width of the cadmium containment is never specified [20], so had to be assumed as equal width to the rhodium foil.

Figure 11: Plot of detector structure in the Janus phase one model, with arrows indicating foil regions. Colour coding as grey for aluminium, blue for cadmium, dark green for sulphur, orange for gold/manganese, and red for rhodium.

The experimental description detailed the individual detectors measurements [20], and the OpenMC model followed this with its addition of activation foils and spectrometers to figure 10. The manganese detectors were only positioned at penetration measurements at locations B2 to B17 as depicted in figure 6, and the sulphur detectors only up to B16. The gold detectors were also positioned at the lateral position's offsets of 25cm, 50cm and 75cm at the shielding distances of B6 and B14, and the rhodium and sulphur detectors also measured these lateral offsets at position B10. OpenMC has no score for the rhodium reaction of $Rh103(n, n')Rh103$ so this detector was not tallied.

As mentioned in section 2.4.2 some minor adjustments needed to be made to the configuration of figure 10 with regards to the manganese detector and spectrometers so that the OpenMC model matches to the experimental description. For the manganese detector the omitted slab was simply set to 'void' in the model. For the spectrometers this was also applied to the slabs preceding the three detectors, additionally the

next slab was moved further back by the distance of the inter joining void region to sit against the following slab.

Unlike the water benchmark model, the detectors in the Janus phase one model lie at several different distances from the neutron source (see figure 6), and so any variance reduction can not be a simple increase towards detector and decrease when away as was done in the water benchmark model. Instead, the efficiency of the neutron population needs to be maintained throughout the shielding in order to reduce error in the more remote detectors, where the neutron population will be declining due to the shielding. Therefore, the weight windows were applied in the OpenMC model as a rectilinear mesh that reduced the upper bound to encourage splitting and less rouletting further through the model. An example of the weight windows functionality involving the manganese detectors is given in appendix section 2.

3.2.2 Source Definition

Figure 12: Diagram of the disc source structure of the fuel contained within the fission plate with X and Y coordinates, intended to model as a circular disc fission source [20].

The dark green region of the fission plate in figure 10 depicts the fuel portion of the Janus phase one model, where the fuel is a 2 mm thick Uranium Aluminium alloy

where the uranium has been enriched to 93% Uranium-235. Its intent is to act as a disc fission neutron source which was modelled as several mesh 'boxes' forming a circular structure, figure 12 shows this in terms of the X and Y coordinates of the fission plate.

The source spectrum is an isotropic Watt fission spectrum with parameters $a = 0.988$ MeV and $b = 2.246$ 1/MeV as defined in equation 6 that corresponds to the fission of Uranium-235. Unlike the water benchmark where weightings of the source definition were provided [18], the Janus phase one model directly uses the OpenMC's implicit Watt spectrum with the parameters as specified. Figure 13 shows this spectrum alongside the Watt spectrum shown previously for Californium's-252's spontaneous fission in section 3.1.2, the two are very similar other than the Janus spectrum being a higher weighting at its peak.

Figure 13: Source spectrum of the Janus disc source (Janus (Watt)) and fellow Watt spectrum imitating Californium-252's fission spectrum (Watt (Californium-252)).

As the simulations model the fission plate as a singular neutron source, the NESTOR background corrective procedure mentioned in section 2.4.2 is not relevant to the simulations. Yet given its imitation of a secondary source of neutrons (the primary neutrons being the leakage neutrons from the NESTOR reactor as discussed in section 2.4.2) the emission strength distribution of this source is not uniform across the structure of figure 13 but instead is heightened in the centre and depletes towards the edges. Figure 14 shows the distribution as absolute source strengths calculated for the fission plate.

	-49.75	-46.58	-43.32	-37.08	-33.92	-27.58	-11.75	-2.25	7.25	16.75	32.58	38.92	42.08	48.42	51.58	54.75
51.44...	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.973E+7	2.994E+7	2.863E+7	0	0	0	0	0	0
47.63...	0	0	0	0	0	3.173E+7	3.496E+7	3.537E+7	3.404E+7	2.975E+7	0	0	0	0	0	0
40.64...	0	0	0	0	3.176E+7	3.711E+7	4.068E+7	4.149E+7	4.015E+7	3.529E+7	2.890E+7	0	0	0	0	0
35.56...	0	0	0	3.186E+7	3.500E+7	4.092E+7	4.514E+7	4.587E+7	4.446E+7	3.925E+7	3.340E+7	2.886E+7	0	0	0	0
31.75...	0	0	3.249E+7	3.635E+7	3.999E+7	4.696E+7	5.197E+7	5.286E+7	5.130E+7	4.555E+7	3.807E+7	3.422E+7	3.099E+7	0	0	0
19.69...	0	3.150E+7	3.575E+7	4.003E+7	4.412E+7	5.202E+7	5.770E+7	5.870E+7	5.699E+7	5.080E+7	4.282E+7	3.873E+7	3.431E+7	2.970E+7	0	0
15.88...	3.040E+7	3.322E+7	3.769E+7	4.223E+7	4.660E+7	5.505E+7	6.110E+7	6.215E+7	6.034E+7	5.387E+7	4.559E+7	4.133E+7	3.673E+7	3.188E+7	2.550E+7	0
5.29...	3.132E+7	3.427E+7	3.893E+7	4.364E+7	4.815E+7	5.684E+7	6.304E+7	6.412E+7	6.227E+7	5.563E+7	4.710E+7	4.270E+7	3.792E+7	3.287E+7	2.932E+7	0
-5.29...	3.226E+7	3.325E+7	3.784E+7	4.239E+7	4.669E+7	5.491E+7	6.079E+7	6.183E+7	6.009E+7	5.364E+7	4.523E+7	4.084E+7	3.607E+7	3.107E+7	2.751E+7	0
-15.88...	0	3.136E+7	3.574E+7	4.001E+7	4.400E+7	5.157E+7	5.701E+7	5.802E+7	5.643E+7	5.031E+7	4.221E+7	3.795E+7	3.331E+7	2.943E+7	0	0
-19.69...	0	0	3.182E+7	3.562E+7	3.912E+7	4.572E+7	5.053E+7	5.149E+7	5.013E+7	4.461E+7	3.713E+7	3.317E+7	2.887E+7	0	0	0
-31.75...	0	0	0	3.004E+7	3.299E+7	3.855E+7	4.267E+7	4.357E+7	4.247E+7	3.766E+7	3.101E+7	2.748E+7	0	0	0	0
-35.56...	0	0	0	0	2.896E+7	3.396E+7	3.770E+7	3.855E+7	3.758E+7	3.320E+7	2.712E+7	0	0	0	0	0
-40.64...	0	0	0	0	0	2.745E+7	3.072E+7	3.150E+7	3.067E+7	2.685E+7	0	0	0	0	0	0
-47.63...	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.458E+7	2.525E+7	2.448E+7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
51.44...	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Figure 14: Schematic of disc source structure of fission plate with the absolute source strengths of each source box, where the neutron emission is stronger towards the centre of the structure [20].

Note these strengths are volume normalised to the defined mesh box, where the coordinate points in the X axis are subtly different from figure 13. The strengths in figure 14 have been calculated, rather than directly measured, so as to normalise the fuel region to a total power of 1 watt: so, the units of the absolute strengths in figure 14 are strictly $n/cm^3/s/Watt$. Whilst the fuel region was geometrical as defined by figure 12 in the OpenMC Janus Phase One model, the actual source definition was defined as several sources as per figure 14.

4 Results and Analysis: The Water Benchmark

4.1 The Scintillator: Experimental Comparison

In the water benchmark experiment the scintillator measured the neutron spectrum above 1 MeV as the neutron flux value, where the flux was recorded across 19 energy groups and normalised to the average lethargy of said groups. The concept of neutron lethargy is often used to simplify energy groups schemes, as an independent variable that describes a particles gain of 'lethargy' (or loss of energy) in a scattering process as a fraction of its current energy rather than as a fixed amount [5]. The OpenMC code returns the neutron flux tally in units of 'n-cm/source particle' so these needs to be volume normalised as well as scaled by the total source strength to match the experimental readings. The former can be calculated manually and the neutron emission for the source specification of this model is known to be 1.048×10^8 neutrons per second [18].

A model of the water benchmark experiment in the code MCBEND [18] was constructed to evaluate the Jeff2.2 library [25] and the results from this, as well as the MCNP model, will be used to help evaluate OpenMC's performance against the experimental readings. Note that due to the limited materials in the Jeff2.2 library the source in the MCBEND model is not Californium-252 but Uranium-238.

Figure 15 shows the flux distribution from the experimental measurements and against simulations performed in OpenMC, MCNP and MCBEND. Note that the first bin (of upper bound 1.05 MeV) has been removed from this analysis as the bin width was inconsistent between the codes and experiment, so this energy bin was disregarded.

Generally, all three codes show close alignment to the experimental results and follow the trend of the flux distribution well. Regarding OpenMC's agreement to the experimental readings, a comparison can be observed where OpenMC underestimates at low energy and then transitions, at around 1.97 MeV, to then overestimate the flux. In particular, above 7 MeV the OpenMC tallied flux is consistently above the experimentally measured equivalent by a factor of 1.2, 1.3 and then 1.4 by the respective energy increases. Very good accordance is seen in the 3.5 MeV to 7 MeV region where many of the the values agree within one σ of uncertainty. At lower energies some discrepancy is seen, especially at 2.53 MeV, where there is an overestimation of a factor 1.2 on OpenMC's part.

Figure 15: Neutron spectrum in the experimental groups from the experiments data (green), the tallies of OpenMC (blue), MCNP (orange) and MCBEND (purple).

Considering the error both from the OpenMC simulation and the experimental readings, both have poor error at the high energies where the flux drops, and so there is error above 10% at the two highest energy bins from the OpenMC results (upper bounds of 8.83 MeV and 10 MeV) and singly at the highest bin from the experimental data. The deviations in flux here as factors of 1.3 and 1.4 are not particularly remarkable against the rest of the nearby energy bins, and these points seem to follow the flux distribution perfectly well in figure 15. Yet these results could certainly be considered unreliable as per table 1; otherwise, all results can be considered reliable with error below 10%.

The MCNP flux results have a similar pattern of underestimation then overestimation throughout the energy levels, and follow the expected error profile where the flux dropping at high energy increases the statistical error. Like OpenMC the two highest bins tallied from MCNP have error above 10%. The MCBEND flux results are often lower in value than the other codes and so underestimate the measured flux a lot more, especially in the 1.19 to 2.23 MeV range. Hence, the errors from the MCBEND results break 10% against the energy increase sooner than the other two codes. At 10 MeV there is an outlying value where the MCBEND code has overestimated the flux relative to the experimental data and the other codes. This may be due to poor statistical error, of 13.4% for this value, or instead a fundamental difference in how MCBEND has modelled the neutron transport. But not enough information on the MCBEND model [18] is provided to determine what exactly has caused this.

Figure 16 shows the C/M ratios as the comparison of all the codes to the experimental results, where the error bars are derived by error propagation from the uncertainties of both the simulations and measurements. Recall from section 2 that the results from the codes are not directly measured like the experimental results, but rather are derived from a normal distribution. In an accurate scenario the mean μ of this distribution would be the experimental measurement but the tallies would still deviate with error σ .

Figure 16: Calculated to measured ratios of energy bins from simulation in OpenMC (blue), MCNP (orange) and MCBEND (purple).

What is clearer in figure 16 is the worsening error at the higher energies; this can be seen by how the codes appear to diverge away from each other's and more explicitly lie outside of each others errors. Before this many of the values overlay within their own error ranges whilst the flux was sufficiently high.

In terms of the ratio values themselves a clear trend is seen for all the codes where at low energy there is underestimation that becomes overestimation at higher energy. Both the OpenMC and MCNP codes appear to fluctuate around a value very close to unity, whilst the MCBEND results tendency for underestimation means for this code the mean μ is likely to be lower than unity. The consistency between the OpenMC and MCNP derived flux is clear in figure 16 but the OpenMC has slightly more deviation against unity.

In terms of the total flux measured/tallied ratio OpenMC tallied a slightly overestimated flux with a total C/M ratio of (1.06 ± 0.01) , whilst MCNP tallied a marginally closer flux with (1.03 ± 0.02) . The MCBEND code indeed underestimates the flux with a total ratio of (0.964 ± 0.007) . Although the comparison to experiment is fairly good for all three codes, MCNP is technically the closest and OpenMC overestimates more than

MCBEND underestimates.

Recalling that the simulations use different cross sectional data libraries and that OpenMC's is more modern, it is worth considering if it is actually the libraries responsible for the slight difference in ratios seen between the codes. However, OpenMC's simulation when using the same data library as MCNP (ENDFB7.1) returns a total ratio of (1.08 ± 0.02) . When using the Jeff3.3 library, the OpenMC ratio is reduced to its most accurate value of (1.04 ± 0.01) . While it could therefore be argued that the ENDFB7.1 library is indeed less accurate, OpenMC has still overestimated the flux more than MCNP even when using the same data library.

Overall, the three Monte Carlo codes have modelled the experiment very well and clearly follow the flux distribution in the experimental group scheme, despite some divergence seen at high energy. The MCNP code proved to have the best accuracy albeit with minor overestimation of the total experimental flux measured, and the MCBEND code had underestimated the experiments total flux to a similar degree. OpenMC was not obviously erroneous in any way (e.g unlike the outlier from MCBEND at 10 MeV) but had overestimated the flux slightly more than MCNP.

4.2 The Scintillator: OpenMC vs MCNP

In the Monte Carlo simulations, the scintillator detector is modelled as a sample cell of hydrogen and carbon that is set to score neutron flux over the full energy spectrum of 1×10^{-10} MeV to 20 MeV. Both the OpenMC and MCNP models tallied this also in 640 energy groups, whilst the MCBEND model only tallied in the experimental groups seen in section 4.1. In contrast this section looks more in depth at the flux distributions from the OpenMC and MCNP codes without reference to the experimental results, as there is no experimental data provided in this finer energy bin structure [18].

As seen previously, the OpenMC and MCNP codes produced very similar flux distributions (in the experimental groups) that were close to the experimental readings. Figure 17 shows the flux distributions now in the 640 group scheme tallied across the range 0 to 13 MeV (above this very little flux was tallied).

Good accordance is seen between the codes where both show an incline up to 2 MeV and subsequent decline which is to be expected given the source definition (described in section 3.1.2). The distribution from OpenMC has some outlying inconsistent high flux values that are deviated from the main trend in the 4 to 7 MeV range. The discrepancies seen from OpenMC in figure 17 may indicate that the moderation applied in the OpenMC simulation is not quite as consistent as in MCNP. But nevertheless they have cancelled out sufficiently for the codes to accord well in section 1.4. However, it is plausible this is still present in figure 15 given the greater flux tallied from OpenMC. Yet the alteration of bin structure has certainly reduced this effect, as the deviation was

not as apparent in figure 15 or 16.

Figure 17: Flux distributions from the OpenMC (blue) and MCNP (orange) simulation in the fine group structure for the full energy range

Figure 18: Flux distributions from the OpenMC (blue) and MCNP (orange) simulation in the fine group structure for the thermal energy range

In addition, both codes have high flux tallies at very low energy, and figure 18 shows this as the exclusively thermal neutron range as 0 to 1 eV. Both codes show the presence of thermal scattering with the peak in flux that centres on 0.1 eV, due to the high flux of this peak it is also associated to good error whereas much of the low energy presence seen in figure 17 is of poor error. It seems outside of the main distribution of figure 18,

both codes have tallied a thermal neutron presence at the detector. In regard to the fast range measured as predominantly shown in figure 17, this presence is rather low hence the difficulty for many of the tallies to gain adequate error.

Overall, the OpenMC and MCNP codes are remarkably consistent in their neutron transport for both the fast and thermal neutron range. The only discrepancy between the distributions seen is the deviated high flux values tallied in OpenMC as mentioned for figure 17. This would indicate slightly different scattering/moderation has been simulated but such has to be somewhat expected with an alternate code. When repeating the OpenMC simulation with different data libraries (both ENDFB7.1 and Jeff.33) the flux distribution from OpenMC in figures 17 and 18 was not altered significantly. Therefore, this discrepancy can only be considered an observation rather than as a defined issue for OpenMC, as when using larger energy bins (as done in section 4.1) OpenMC was well agreeing to the experimental results.

4.3 The Sulphur Detector: Experimental Comparison

Figure 19: Cross sectional data for sulphur neutron capture - proton production reaction, specifically from the ENDFB/V-11.1 library [21].

In the water benchmark experiment the sulphur detector made measurements of the $S^{32}(n,p)P^{32}$ reaction in the units of reaction rate per source particle per source atom. The OpenMC simulation only normalises to source particle, so the atomic content normalization was done manually after the tally results were collected. This is a threshold reaction so the energy range of the neutrons is limited to above 0.639 MeV as one can see in figure 19 that depicts the associated cross section [21]. This was assigned as

the minimum energy of the tally in the OpenMC model, and the upper energy bounds was set at 20 MeV as the maximum energy of the source spectrum.

Whilst figure 19 gives an indication of the reaction rate profile expected one must also consider the flux distribution as previously analysed by the scintillator in section 4.1 and 4.2. The actual reaction rate Γ measured over a volume V will be proportional to both quantities of flux Φ and cross section Σ as indicated by equation 8. Note the dependence on the volume of the detector V so the normalisation to sulphur atomic content is done to eliminate this.

$$\Gamma \propto \Phi \Sigma V \quad (8)$$

With the source specification of the simulations as defined in section 3.1.1, the experiment measured a total reaction rate value of $(8.55 \pm 0.51) \times 10^{-31}$ Bq/source particle/sulphur atom. The total reaction rate tallied from OpenMC is very similar as $(1.12 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-30}$ Bq/source particle/sulphur atom, whilst the MCBEND model tallied a total value of $(1.01 \pm 0.03) \times 10^{-30}$ Bq/source particle/sulphur atom. Both have overstated the reaction rate slightly and, hence; the codes derive C/M ratios of (1.31 ± 0.08) and (1.18 ± 0.08) for OpenMC and MCBEND respectively. As well as the σ error from the codes tallies, the experimental data brought a standard deviation error of 6% to the ratios [18].

Given equation 8 the simulated neutron flux will interact with the $S32(n,p)P32$ cross sectional data that is provided by the data library, so it is worth considering what impact using different data libraries will have on the C/M ratios. When changing the OpenMC library from ENDFB8.0 the C/M ratio is altered to (1.34 ± 0.01) for ENDF7.1 and (1.28 ± 0.01) for JEFF-3.3. While there are some small differences: ENDFB.7.1 has increased the ratio slightly whilst the JEFF-3.3 library instead decreased the ratio, neither bring the ratio down as well as the MCBEND ratio.

Looking at figure 15 the overestimation's from OpenMC in the range 6.87 MeV to 10 MeV are more significant than when in lower energy. The cross section of figure 19 climbs more steeply in this higher energy region so the flux overestimation is likely the cause of OpenMC's reaction rate for sulphur also being overestimated. Aside from the single outlier, the MCBEND C/M ratios in this energy range are lower compared to OpenMC's and so the overestimation of reaction rate from MCBEND is not as significant. Therefore, one can say that so far the flux overestimation appears to be an idiosyncrasy of the OpenMC code, rather than from any particular data library that has been used, and is the main reason for the overstatement of neutron activation from OpenMC.

5 Results and Analysis: The Janus Phase One Benchmark

5.1 The Spectrometers: Experimental Comparison

The spectrometers measured the neutron flux across 43 energy groups at the detector positions of B6 and B10, and across 33 energy groups at B14 as depicted in figure 6 (all with no lateral offsetting). The results for the spectrometers are not normalised to the 1-watt source, so the conversion factor between the NESTOR reactor and the fission plate [20] is used to establish the absolute plate power at 17.4 watts; the source particle normalisation is then done in reference to this power. All the flux values are also normalised to the average lethargy of the energy groups and the detector volume.

Figures 20, 21 and 22 show the flux profile from the experimental results, the OpenMC and MCNP simulations across the energy groups at each detector location. In these figures the energy range is limited from 0 to 3 MeV as very little flux was recorded above this. Error bars derived by error propagation of the experimental error and the simulations statistical error are included, yet they are often so small that they are not visible for much of the data.

Figure 20: Flux distributions from OpenMC(blue)), MCNP(orange) and experimental results(green) for the spectrometer at B6.

Figure 21: Flux distributions from OpenMC(blue), MCNP(orange) and experimental results(green) for the spectrometer at B10.

Figure 22: Flux distributions from OpenMC(blue), MCNP(orange) and experimental results(green) for the spectrometer at B14.

Both codes show the expected distribution of the flux and clearly follow the experimental readings, especially at the high energy tail where in all three figures the flux scales down fairly coherently from all three distributions. As seen in section 4, both codes tend to slightly overestimate the flux, and this becomes more apparent with greater distance across figures 20 to 22. MCNP has a seeming outlier at 0.0525 MeV where the start of the distribution begins much lower than the experimental results or the OpenMC tallies, otherwise the distributions from the codes appear fairly consistent with one another. Additionally, both codes agree less with the experiment as the detector moves further from the source, and do not simulate the moderation the neutrons experience

quite as well when more shielding is applied. And so the total flux C/M ratios from figures 20 to 22 trend upwards as summarized in table 4.

C/M ratio for OpenMC	C/M ratio for MCNP	Detector Position
(0.95 ± 0.01)	(0.95 ± 0.03)	B6
(1.10 ± 0.01)	(1.10 ± 0.01)	B10
(1.40 ± 0.01)	(1.41 ± 0.02)	B14

Table 4: Total flux C/M ratios derived from the spectrometers of the Janus Phase One model in OpenMC and MCNP.

The ratios of table 4 reflect incredible consistency between the codes, the only point of comparison is at B14 where OpenMC is marginally more accurate. Indeed, the increase in shielding through figures 20 to 22 demonstrates the codes becoming less consistent to one another as well as the experimental data, due to the rising level of neutron scattering events required in the simulations; and the total flux values tallied between the codes reflects this. So at B6 the codes are actually underestimates of the experimental flux and are exact to one another with an OpenMC/MCNP ratio of (1.000 ± 0.002) . At B14 this declines to (0.996 ± 0.006) as MCNP has overstated the flux more relative to OpenMC and the experimental data at this furthest detector. However, this below unity value is also apparent at B10 with an Open/MCNP ratio of (0.997 ± 0.004) , but the rounding involved with the high flux values means the same C/M ratio has been outputted for both codes at B10. Yet this does reflect that after B10 it is MCNP that is overestimating the flux more than OpenMC. However this effect is very minor and only in a few bins in figure 21 and 22 can you see MCNP tallying a higher flux than OpenMC.

It is worth considering the worsening error in figures 20 to 22 as the flux falls and so some of the tallies at B14 are above the recommended 10% for reliable Monte Carlo results, as per table 1. The experimental readings derive uncertainties from random counting statistics as well as from calibrations specific to the detectors [20], and so the error for the spectrometer at B14 is very consistent as 5% for most of the flux readings with 7% and 9% at the two highest energy bins. In contrast the flux tallies from the codes stagger up in error as the flux falls and the error exceeds 10% at 1.19 MeV for OpenMC, and at 1.53 MeV for MCNP. Yet as little contribution to the total flux is made above 1 MeV, this issue of error is more tolerable than if the level of flux was consistent across the full energy range.

Because the codes are generally so consistent to one another it is difficult to see in figures 20 to 22 which is following the experimental distribution better. This is easier to see in the individual C/M ratios from each energy bin a the right hand side of figures

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23, 24 and 25 against the associated flux distributions at each detector.

Figure 23: Flux distributions (left) and associated C/M ratios (right) from OpenMC(blue) and MCNP (orange) for the spectrometer at B6.

Figure 24: Flux distributions (left) and associated C/M ratios (right) from OpenMC(blue) and MCNP (orange) for the spectrometer at B10.

Figure 25: Flux distributions (left) and associated C/M ratios (right) from OpenMC(blue) and MCNP (orange) for the spectrometer at B14.

In the right hand side of figures 23 to 25 one can see that OpenMC is more consistent around unity, whereas MCNP diverges from underestimating then overestimating the flux more. As expected at B6 the two codes are fairly even in their fluctuation around unity, even if MCNP's less agreeing flux distribution is starting to be seen. At B10 and B14 the ratios trend upwards and both diverge off around 1 MeV, before this energy the ratios are more consistent with one another. Rather figures 23 to 25 are showing significant overestimation only in the high energy tail in which the C/M ratios will be exaggerated due to the relatively lower flux in this region. Yet, figures 23 to 25 do reflect that OpenMC is centering around unity moreso than MCNP. So despite the very consistent total C/M ratios t is OpenMC that is better matched to the shape of the experimental flux distribution, whereas MCNP is more misshapen and so appears more diverging.

Recall that the simulations have again used different cross section libraries as described in section 1.4, so it is worth considering if it is actually the more modern library responsible for OpenMC's better accordance to the experimental results. OpenMC's simulation when using the same data library as MCNP (ENDFB7.1) and the Jeff3.3 library returned the total C/M ratios of table 5.

C/M ratio for OpenMC (ENDFB7.1)	C/M ratio for OpenMC (Jeff3.3)	Detector Position
(0.96±0.01)	(0.95±0.01)	B6
(1.11±0.01)	(1.13±0.01)	B10
(1.40±0.01)	(1.42±0.01)	B14

Table 5: Total flux C/M ratios derived from spectrometers of Janus Phase One model in OpenMC, with the OpenMC library altered to ENDFB7.1. and JEFF3.3.

In terms of agreement with the experimental results; the alterations in the ratios at B6 and B10 from ENDFB7.1 do not improve or worsen the accuracy OpenMC has shown nor alter its comparison to MCNP. The Jeff3.3 library has raised the flux slightly at the locations of B10 and B14 so this library is actually the least accurate.

5.2 The Activation Detectors: Experimental Comparison

All the activation detector readings are normalised to the detector volume as the atomic content, so the respective reaction rates are measured in units of $Bq/atom$. Unlike the spectrometers, the activation detector measurements are normalised to the plate power and so the source particle unit correction is simply the neutron emission rate according to 1 watt for the fuel material, which was calculated to be $7.61E+10$ neutrons per second.

The location identities of the detectors (B1,B2,B3 etc) as depicted in figure 6 will be replaced by the actual source to detector distances in this section. These values are taken as to the distance from the centre of the fission plate to the furthest point of the detector (for the activation detectors this was the rear face of the aluminium carrier). Also note this section only concerns the penetration measurements of the activation detectors and not the lateral readings.

5.2.1 The Manganese Foil

Figure 26: Cross sectional data for Mn55 neutron capture with gamma emission, specifically from the ENDFB/V-11.1 library [21].

Figure 26 shows the $Mn55(n, \gamma)Mn56$ reaction cross section which is decreasing down from the MeV energy range with resonances at lower energy; clearly this reaction has a strong inverse relation to the neutron energy. The placement of the manganese foils in the shielding configuration brings the neutrons energies to a region of higher cross sections, however given equation 8 and the flux profile seen in section 5.1 it is more likely the reduction in the neutron flux will overpower this.

Figure 27 shows the $Mn55(n, \gamma)Mn56$ reaction rates tallied from OpenMC from three different data libraries alongside the experimental measurements. All distributions show a clear exponential decline which is to be expected given the strong reduction in flux due to the Janus model's shielding, so the flux is clearly more influential than the cross section in figure 27.

Figure 27: Experimental results and OpenMC tallies across three different libraries for the $Mn55(n, \gamma)Mn56$ reaction in the Janus phase one model.

Figure 28: C/M ratios from the simulation values from figure 27.

The distributions of figure 27 are incredibly close and many of the C/M ratios of figure 28 fluctuate around unity, both underestimation and overestimation from OpenMC is seen but the latter is more significant. The ENDFB7.1 library is notably less accurate than the ENDFB8.0 or JEFF3.3 library, but the former was the most consistent with an average C/M ratio of (1.07 ± 0.09) . Despite subtle variation between the libraries the accordance to the experimental data is impressive and all the distributions of reaction rate are clearly following the experimental data.

One may expect the reaction rate to deviate more with distance given section 5.1's establishment of OpenMC's flux through the shielding (summarised in table 4). The cross section (figure 26 climbing with lower neutron energy would also emphasise this. The distributions of 28 do show an upward trend, and this is likely to be a combination

of the flux overestimation from OpenMC and how the reaction rate are decreasing in value.

Ultimately, the manganese activation has shown very little, if any, deviation from the experimental data for two of the libraries used. The exception is of course ENDFB7.1, yet as the oldest library this is almost certainly due to inaccurate cross sectional data rather than a reflection on OpenMC.

5.2.2 The Gold Foil

Figure 29: Cross sectional data for Au197 neutron capture with gamma emission, specifically from the ENDFB/V-11.1 library [21].

Figure 29 shows the $Au197(n, \gamma)Au198$ reaction cross section [21] which is remarkably similar to the manganese of figure 26. Figure 30 shows the $Au197(n, \gamma)Au198$ reaction rates tallied from OpenMC from the three different libraries alongside the experimental measurements, and figure 31 shows the resulting C/M ratios.

A similar analysis to the manganese reaction can be applied to the gold reaction, although there is much clearer overestimation in the gold reaction rates. Therefore, all the C/M ratios of figure 31 are shifted further from unity relative to figure 28. The trend upwards with distances is also more emphasised as the variation of reaction rate is greater in OpenMC's results than the experiments. As the neutron flux should be consistent between the manganese and gold foils due to them being in the same location, one can interpret that this is the result of less accurate cross sectional information for gold than manganese.

Figure 31 does show this overstatement consistently between all the data libraries

whereas figure 27 had a clear library of least accuracy in ENDFB7.1. For the gold reaction it is the Jeff3.3 data library that is most accurate with an average ratio of (1.76 ± 0.28) and the ENDFB8.0 library is now actually the least accurate with (1.95 ± 0.24) . Yet given the OpenMC's results in figure 30 are all so consistent to one another, one can postulate if the gold cross sectional information has been updated since ENDFB7.1 to the level that the data for manganese clearly had.

Figure 30: Experimental results and OpenMC tallies across three different libraries for the $Au^{197}(n, \gamma)Au^{198}$ reaction in the Janus phase one model.

Figure 31: C/M ratios from the simulation values from figure 30.

5.2.3 The Sulphur Foil

Figure 32: Experimental results and OpenMC tallies across three different libraries for the $S32(n,p)P32$ reaction in the Janus phase one model. The reaction rate axis is set to a logarithmic form due to the serious variation in the experimental to OpenMC results.

Figure 32 shows the $S32(n,p)P32$ reaction rates tallied from OpenMC from the three different libraries alongside the experimental measurements (recall figure 19 as the $S32(n,p)P32$ reaction cross section). The tallies for sulphur are not nearly as well aligned as the other two activation detectors, hence figure 32 has a logarithmic axis for reaction rate as OpenMC has significantly overstated the reaction rates in all three libraries (with one outlying exception). Figure 33 presents the accompanying C/M ratios that shows the difference in the reaction rates measured experimentally vs the OpenMC tallied rates more intelligibly.

Figure 33 clearly shows it is the detectors of closest and furthest range to the source that have most severely overestimated the reaction rate. In the range of B4 to B15 the ratios are more reasonable in being within a factor of 10, although they are mostly higher than the equivalent ratios for the previous gold and manganese foils. Technically the ENDFB8.0 library has the best average ratio of (8.19 ± 14.9) yet due to the great variation of C/M ratio seen in figure 33 the average ratios are of very poor error, and so it is difficult to compare when all three libraries clearly all have problematic results.

Figure 33: C/M ratios from the simulation values from figure 32.

The sulphur detector is the only activation detector not shielded by cadmium and so it is likely the flux reflected in the reaction rates of figure 32 is disproportionately greater than previously seen in figures 27 and 30. Figure 33 also shows overestimation at further distance than the spectrometers previously established, and this was also seen for the other activation foils. Yet the overestimation is by far the most pronounced at the B2 location where the closest data library (Jeff3.3) derives a C/M ratio of (59.3 ± 0.05) .

As B2 is the detector closest to the fission plate, there is no steel shielding experienced here but instead the aluminium frame of the fission plate provides the only barrier between the fuel and B2's sulphur foil. The sulphur foil of B1 (the other side of the fission plate, see figure 6) does have the remainder of the detector arrangement preceding the neutron emission, yet this provides little shielding as a tally taken of the reaction rate here was consistent with B2. This result and figure 33 may be indicating a serious issue with OpenMC's modelling of aluminium, that has caused all the flux felt by the sulphur foil regions of the detector arrangement (figure 11) to be far greater than it should be.

The spectrometer measurements only extend from the location of B6 (23.5 cm in figure 33) and do not record the flux closer to the source. Due to the limited experimental readings of the neutron flux spectrum, it is therefore not possible to compare the flux modelled in OpenMC to the experimental flux surrounding the fission plate, nor establish any discrepancy here as the cause of figure 32.

6 Discussion

This project aimed to bring insight into the neutron transport capabilities of the Monte Carlo code OpenMC. This was done by using the experimental results from two quality assessed SINBAD benchmarks in comparison to results from OpenMC simulations, and also from accompanying MCNP and MCBEND models. The results from the Water Benchmark model were analysed in section 4 and the same was done for the Janus Phase One model in section 5.

In section 4.1 and 4.2 it was seen that the MCNP and OpenMC codes overestimated the neutron flux from the experimental results with total flux C/M ratios of (1.03 ± 0.02) and (1.06 ± 0.01) respectively. The results from the MCBEND model instead underestimated the flux with a total C/M ratio of (0.954 ± 0.007) . The OpenMC results were less accurate than MCNP, and the MCBEND model had underestimated the flux to a similar degree that OpenMC had overstated the flux. In terms of the water benchmark's experimental description, the lack of certainty about whether a background corrective procedure is required for the measurements [15] might indicate a reason behind both the MCNP and OpenMC results. Yet also considering the results from the MCBEND model it seems unlikely this has had an effect on the accuracy of the results.

In both the fast and thermal neutron ranges the OpenMC and MCNP codes were very much in accordance with one other, and the slight overstatement from OpenMC was believed to be the result of some divergent high flux tallies seen in the 4 to 7 MeV range. All this really proved was that in OpenMC's simulation the neutron moderation procedure for light water was non exact to MCNP's. Yet the results from these codes were similar and very well aligned to the experimental data, and one can feel confident that section 4 demonstrated very respectable neutron transport simulation in light water from OpenMC.

Section 5.1 reviewed the neutron transport from OpenMC and MCNP for the Janus Phase One model, which predominantly features steel providing much lower neutron moderation compared with water. Again, both the MCNP and OpenMC results followed the neutron flux distribution as from the experimental data very well and the total C/M ratios were incredibly consistent between the codes, and are summarised in table 4. With further investigation into the tallies of the codes with increasing levels of shielding, OpenMC was found to be marginally more accurate than MCNP.

In the Janus Phase One model, the detector B6's shielding was limited to only mild steel (aside from the source region) and for both codes the tallies from this detector were the most accurate. Further from the fission plate the materials become more complex with additives of nickel, phosphorus, sulphur, molybdenum and chromium included in the additional stainless steel shields. Although this may just be the nature of Monte Carlo simulations where more randomly predicted scattering phenomena is necessary for tallying at B14 relative to at B6. The fact both codes behave similarly throughout the distance and are also the most consistent to one another at B6 would suggest the

latter; and one would require experimental data of exclusively stainless steel shielding at B6 to directly prove this.

Both the detector B6's fission plate separation and the water benchmarks detector to source distance were very similar (23.52cm and 25.40cm respectively), and the level of accuracy from OpenMC was very similar for these tallies. This would imply that there is no significant variation between the mediums of steel and water regarding OpenMC's neutron transport capability. But one would need to repeat the water benchmark model with the detectors at a further distance setting to validate this. At larger distances of steel OpenMC did not simulate neutron transport quite as accurately as the water benchmark standard; but OpenMC's correlation to MCNP in section 5.1 was very reassuring that OpenMC is a perfectly viable choice of code for neutron transport in steel.

For both these benchmarks, when reviewing OpenMC's capability for neutron activation any flux overestimation would carry over into overstating the reaction rates. For the water benchmark the MCBEND model gave a more accurate tally of sulphur activation with a C/M ratio of (1.18 ± 0.08) compared to OpenMC's (1.31 ± 0.08) . In the Janus Phase One model gamma emission was also recorded with manganese and gold foil detectors, and both of OpenMC's tallies showed very good accordance to the experimental measurements with average ratios of (1.07 ± 0.09) and (1.76 ± 0.28) respectively (taken from the most accurate data library in each case). In addition, OpenMC's results in section 5.2 did show that the overestimation of flux increased throughout the shielding as was seen in section 5.1, but this effect was minor in its deviation from the experimental readings. Whilst the gamma emission activation OpenMC displayed was very agreeable, the analysis of OpenMC's capability for proton emission proved more complex. Indeed, whilst the OpenMC sulphur activation for the water benchmark was not unreasonable, this may suggest that other codes that do not have an inclination towards flux overestimation are likely to produce more accurate proton emission tallying.

The same sulphur activation was also measured in the Janus Phase One model and was greatly overestimated by OpenMC. All the reaction rates tallied from OpenMC were significantly higher than the experimental readings and this was especially prevalent for the B2 detector closest to the fission plate. As OpenMC's overestimation of the $S^{32}(n, p)P^{32}$ reaction for the water benchmark was nowhere near as problematic, the cause of this discrepancy was implied to be specific to the Janus Phase One model rather than OpenMC's capability with respect to sulphur activation. The sulphur foils placement in the detector structure (figure 11) meant this particular detector experienced much less neutron moderation and absorption than the fellow activation foils. Hence, the subsequent tallying may be an enhanced effect of OpenMC's flux overestimation.

It is also possible that OpenMC does not model aluminium (as the fission plate material) to provide the level of shielding it should; perhaps this materials presence as

the measurement tube casing in the water benchmark model contributed to OpenMC's overestimation here. Yet due to the lack of experimental information on the flux in this region of the Janus phase one model, whether OpenMC is indeed overestimating the flux around the aluminium can not be validated. One could also speculate that potentially the experimental set up included some details that were not reported on and therefore not included in the model in the source region. In particular, the quality assessment of Janus Phase One model indicated lack of detail in detector arrangement, so it is possible the detector configuration was not reproduced in OpenMC as it should and as a result the sulphur foil has suffered much greater neutron flux than it should.

This project also aimed to explore OpenMC using different data libraries to further evaluate this code in comparison to others; the MCBEND code used the JEFF2.2 library and MCNP the ENDFB7.1 library throughout whilst OpenMC mainly used the ENDFB8.0 library. However, the flux behaviour stayed present throughout and was clearly inherent to OpenMC rather than due to a particular library choice, and no change of library altered the accuracy between the codes relative to one another. Table 6 and 7 summarizes the accuracy of each library used in OpenMC for each benchmark model. Note in the latter that there is no indication given for sulphur activation, this is due to the poor errors in the ratios derived from all three libraries for this detector.

Water Benchmark Model	ENDFB8.0	ENDFB7.1	JEFF3.3
Neutron Flux		0	X
Neutron Activation: $S^{32}(n,p)S^{33}$		0	X

Table 6: Evaluation of Data Libraries used in OpenMC for the Water Benchmark Model, X is an indication of highest accuracy whilst 0 of least accuracy.

Janus Phase One Model	ENDFB8.0	ENDFB7.1	JEFF3.3
Neutron Flux	-	-	0
Neutron Activation: $Mn^{55}(n,y)Mn^{56}$	X	0	
Neutron Activation: $Au^{197}(n,y)Au^{198}$	0		X
Neutron Activation: $S^{32}(n,p)S^{33}$	N/A	N/A	N/A

Table 7: Evaluation of Data Libraries used in OpenMC for the Janus Phase One Model, X is an indication of highest accuracy, 0 of least accuracy and - for equal matching.

Table 6 clearly shows that for the water benchmark model the Jeff3.3 library is the best choice, due to this models predominant feature of light water it is likely this library would prove the most accurate for several light water based models in OpenMC.

Recall from section 5.1 the change in accuracy for the ENFB8.0 and JEFF3.3 libraries seen between the gold and manganese activation; this is also the only instance in

table 7 where the most modern library (ENDFB8.0) was the least accurate. This may suggest gold activation will be consistently less accurate than for same for manganese regardless of library choice.

Overall, this project did not see one particular data library to consistently improve results. The ENDFB7.1 library was often seen impairing OpenMC's accuracy, but as the oldest data library used by OpenMC this was not particularly surprising. Tables 6 and 7 do indicate that the age of the library is a good starting point in evaluating its accuracy. But further care should be taken when selecting a library in terms of the construct of the simulation, e.g the ENDFB8.0 library may not be good choice for a simulation involving both gold and manganese activation.

This project also hopes to provide a more general and practical review of OpenMC as a viable code, in addition to the statements made in section 2.2. When constructing the water benchmark model, a significant issue with one of the OpenMC statistical functions [11] was found (detailed in appendix section 10.3), where the interpolation definition was not reproduced as expected in the simulation. This seemingly minor issue had serious repercussions for the results of the simulation where the flux profile tallied from OpenMC was completely unexpected and inaccurate (figure 39). It is speculated that a bug in the code was unfortunately stumbled across during the modelling stage of this project. Given the nature of the OpenMC code and its development as open-source, this is unlikely to be one-off event and the much less rigid quality assurance of this code should be taken into account for OpenMC validation. It is therefore a subjective choice on whether the benefits outweigh potential problems or limitations that using OpenMC brings. Section 2.2 summarized the usability of OpenMC and section 10.3 is a good indication of a problem encountered when using the code.

7 Conclusion

In this project OpenMC has proven itself adept at neutron transport with many of the C/M ratios being close to unity and clear distribution alignment to the experimental results was often seen. Although it cannot be denied an propensity for flux overestimation has been established, yet whenever OpenMC displayed this, so did the code MCNP. Hence, the scope of this project has very much determined OpenMC to be about on par with MCNP regarding neutron transport.

OpenMC's overstating of neutron flux may lead to over predictions of dose and neutron irradiation from OpenMC that is more significant than other codes, yet this is not necessarily undesirable as with regards to radiation protection and shielding design this over estimation can be tolerated as it is better to be conservative when estimating acceptable doses. However, overestimation can lead to over engineering shielding or radiation protection solutions. But any preference for either estimation is entirely subjective to the application, and a truly accurate code is still the most beneficial for all.

Whilst OpenMC's neutron transport capability is certainly promising, more investigation

is advised to better understand how consistent the flux overestimation is. As this project also saw similar results when using MCNP this is not necessarily a career-ending conclusion for OpenMC. A suitable calibration could be applied or as in the example above; overestimation can be desirable from a safety perspective and a level of tolerance is allowed depending on what the code is being used for. In particular, such an investigation would want to consider if the overestimation becomes unreasonable when the model provides limited neutron moderation and absorption.

One would also want to consider the how specific the overestimation's observed are to the materials concerned in the two benchmarks of this project; or is the overstatement inherent to OpenMC regardless of material, geometry or data library etc. As this project did see flux underestimation in steel contrary to overestimation in water at a similar detector source separation; the level of neutron moderating power of the material is likely a factor in this.

In response to these questions, other SINBAD experiments [15] warranting consideration may include the Winfrith Graphite Benchmark Experiment to elaborate on the modelling of graphite in OpenMC. The Janus Phase One did include this material but given the detector locations only analysis could be made between the steel types (the graphite was part of the source region that was not directly analysed). The medium of graphite also lies between steel and water in terms of its moderating power on neutrons, so the analysis of such may contribute to establishing a trend in OpenMC's estimations. The Janus Phase Six benchmark incorporates the familiar mild steels slabs of Phase One but also tanks of sodium in the shielding configuration may be considered. Given sodium's frequent presence in fast reactor coolant systems this is another material of note for OpenMC's neutron flux modelling validation. Additionally, from a shielding perspective the NAIÄDE 1 Concrete Benchmark would be a very desirable choice for validating OpenMC with the common biological shield of concrete. Such investigation would therefore want to extend outside of neutron transport and also into the gamma transport capability of OpenMC. Finally, the OKTAVIAN Aluminum sphere would be a wise choice for investigation given the suspicion raised with OpenMC's modelling of aluminum in the Janus Phase One Model. Note that the NAIÄDE 1 Concrete Benchmark is not yet quality assessed whereas all former benchmarks mentioned are considered to be of category one quality [16]. The need for an OpenMC validation regarding the concrete may very well outweigh the validation the quality review procedure provides, yet this would need to be considered if this benchmark was considered in comparison to the results of this project or any other classification "one" benchmarks.

Overall, this project completed what it set out to do where the modelling of two SINBAD benchmark showed that OpenMC can adequately model neutron transport in water and in a number of steels. The neutron activation of OpenMC was also largely satisfactory, although a significant issue was seen with one of the activation foils and the cause can only be theorized within the scope of this project. However, further work is required to understand how OpenMC simulates neutron transport within other materials as discussed.

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9 References

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10 Appendix

10.1 Janus Phase One Benchmark: Neutrons in Fast and Thermal Reactors

Figure 34: Two neutron spectra as from a typical thermal LWR (blue) and of a sodium cooled fast breeder reactor (red). The elastic scattering cross section of sodium is also shown [26].

In the Janus Phase One benchmark experiment the NESTOR reactor serves as a primary neutron leakage source for the fission plate of the shielding configuration. As a thermal reactor, the MeV component of this neutron spectrum will be much smaller relative to that of a fast reactor. As the Janus Phase One benchmark was an experiment conducted to support the shielding designs of sodium-cooled fast reactors, the thermal spectrum is adapted by the fission plate and spectral filter portion of the shielding configuration to a spectrum that is fast reactor typical [20]. Figure 34 shows both spectra in terms of neutron energy against flux, for a typical thermal reactor (specifically an LWR) and a sodium-cooled fast breeder reactor.

Due to the use of a moderator the majority of neutrons present in a thermal reactor

classify as thermal, that is they are in thermal equilibrium with their surroundings. When assuming a Maxwell Boltzmann distribution as equation 9, the most probable energy will be 0.025 eV for a surrounding (room) temperature of 293 K [24]. On the other hand, a fast spectrum may be described by the prompt neutron fission spectrum of equation 10, the most probable energy will be 0.7 MeV where the majority of the spectrum sits in the MeV range [5].

$$p(E) = 2\pi\sqrt{E}/(\pi KT)^{3/2}\exp(-E/kT) \quad (9)$$

$$p(E) = 0.453\exp(-1.036E)\sinh(\sqrt{2.29E}) \quad (10)$$

Note the relation between the fast spectrum and the scattering cross section in figure 34, particularly at the resonance around 0.005 MeV. Because of the much higher energy flux present, in a fast reactor the neutron spectrum is highly affected by the coolant in operation and can appear drastically different between coolants of varying scattering/moderating properties (defined by the appropriate cross section). For example gas-cooled reactors have significantly harder neutron spectra than in sodium-cooled reactors [26]. Hence, the Janus phase one experiments specificity in reproducing a spectrum typical of a fast reactor that is being cooled by sodium.

10.2 OpenMC Weight Windows: Manganese Activation foils

The weight windows function was applied to the Janus phase one benchmark model as a method of counteracting the decrease in neutron population, and therefore rise in error, throughout the shielding configuration. Figure 35 shows the error derived from the tallies at the detector locations (given by distance to source) both with and without weight windows.

Figure 35: Two error distributions taken from tallies of manganese detectors before any weight windows were added to the model (purple) and after (green).

In figure 35 an incline in error seen in both distributions but is more significant before any variance reduction was applied; where the error diverges above 25% at the highest distances. With the addition of the weight windows, the error profile flattens out as the biasing effects of the weight windows (splitting and rouletting of the particles) counteract against the neutron population fall. So, the error is slightly increased at the lower distances but remains steadier as the neutron population falls throughout the shielding.

Figure 36 shows the associated reaction rates of figure 35, this is to ensure the addition of weight windows has not altered the results in any way, which they clearly have not as the results overlap one another.

Figure 36: Reaction rates taken from tallies of manganese detectors before any weight windows were added to the model (purple) and after (green).

10.3 Water Benchmark: Conversion of the Source Emission

During the modelling of the water benchmark model, part of the source definition had to be altered after an issue was discovered with one of OpenMC's statistical functions. The tabular function [27] was used to call a histogram interpolation to define the emission spectrum of Californium-252. Figure 37 shows this spectrum as defined as a histogram in the experimental information, so the data points correspond to the upper energy of the associated energy bin.

Figure 37: Emission spectrum from experimental information.

Yet the lack of equal bounds to weightings standard to a histogram distribution seemingly caused an erroneous default probability to be assigned to the last bin. The manual explicitly describes a scenario where the length of the parameters are the same (in this case the energy values defining the edges of the bins, and the associated probabilities of the energy bins), where the last weighting value will be ignored [27].

Figure 38: Emission spectra from figure 37 with the additional original OpenMC histogram definition of the source emission (OpenMC(Experiment)). Intensity has been set to a logarithmic scale to show the serious deviation in the latter distribution.

Yet figure 38 shows the original emission spectrum (Experiment) from figure 37 alongside the emission spectrum taken from OpenMC with this input (OpenMC(Experiment)).

The latter is tending towards zero at the last energy bin (at upper limit 12.8 MeV) when the probability weighting increases by a factor of 1000 higher than the previous bin. In the case of the manual's description, adding another weighting (the same again as for 12.8 MeV) did not correct the source emission seen.

This high energy bin had a substantial effect on the simulation where the flux spectrum tallied at the sample looked different as to what was expected, figure 39 shows this alongside the MCNP models' equivalent. As the abnormally high emission at the highest energy bin caused less neutrons to be sufficiently moderated to lower energy in OpenMC's simulation. Due to the spectrum being normalised there is much less low energy presence in the source, so the flux tallied is significantly lower below around 7 MeV. Also note the very large flux around 13 MeV of a small but significant neutron contribution that has evaded sufficient moderation. Overall, the incorrect output of OpenMC's tabular function has caused the entire flux profile to have shifted in energy.

Figure 39: Flux distributions tallied at the sample in the water benchmark from the MCNP and OpenMC model with the histogram definition in the source description.

As a result of this observation, the source emission needed to be altered to still follow the experimental definition but not use the tabular function of OpenMC. The source spectrum was changed to be a discrete defined spectrum instead of a histogram, as no associated issues were found using the discrete statistical function of OpenMC [28]. This spectrum retained the exact weightings as the experimentally defined, but instead assigned them to the central energy of the associated bin. This central bins spectrum is shown in figure 40 alongside the experimental spectrum. The distributions are incredibly similar but the slight shift in energy can be seen.

Figure 40: Emission spectrum from experimental information, alongside new OpenMC defined spectrum using a discrete interpolation and the central value of the energy bins (OpenMC(Central bins)).

Figure 41 shows the new flux distribution from OpenMC alongside the MCNP flux, and it is clear the source spectrum's between the codes now match.

Figure 41: Flux distributions when OpenMC source definition was altered to the central bins form instead of the histogram.